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Nanocellulose extraction from rice straw

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Introduction: Agriculture fields such as wood, bast fibers, gasses, along with aquatic animals, algae, fungi, etc. are a major source of component nanocellulose and also a major source of industrial waste which is utilized as adsorbents (1). Rice straw act as a good adsorbent for heavy metal removal due to the presence of binding sites cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin (2). Chemically modified nano-cellulose is processed with 5% NaOH, sodium chlorite for bleaching purposes which is further followed by hydrolyzing the material along with ultrasonication (3). In this research, we studied nanocellulose extraction from rice straw with chemical treatment.

Material and Method: The sample was collected from satrod village Hisar, Haryana. The collected sample was washed with distilled water and grinded in fine material. Now, samples were treated with 8% NaOH for alkali treatment to remove cellulose from lignocellulosic biomass. Bleaching process with 5% NaCl to extract the pure form of cellulose material. Hydrolysis is helped remove the impurities from the sample and washed them with water and continue with ultrasonication and cryocrushing.

Results & Discussions: To convert the into nanocellulose raw material is treated with step by step processes as discussed in methods. The resulting material is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Nanocellulose extraction procedure.

Conclusions: The obtained material is shown that nanocellulose is successfully extracted from rice straw through the process of acid hydrolysis. The extracted material is continued with ultrasonication and cryocrushing.

Keywords: *Nanocellulose, Agriculture Waste, Acid Hydrolysis, Cryocrushing*

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